

[Protocol] Barriers to Case Management Practice and Discourse on Professionalism in Korean Elderly Welfare: A Scoping Review

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Abstract

This study was conducted to diagnose the qualitative limitations and crisis of professionalism in case management practice amidst the quantitative expansion of elderly care services. A scoping review was performed on 32 selected articles using domestic and international databases. The results revealed: First, research trends show an explosive increase in related studies since 2022, with a recent emergence of studies on AI and technology convergence. Second, thematic analysis identified a significant gap between the ideal roles (advocate, counselor) and the reality (administrator) of case managers. Third, role ambiguity with healthcare professionals and lack of information sharing were identified as major barriers hindering integrated practice. This study suggests establishing a professional practice system beyond administrative management, enacting legal grounds for care management, and introducing future-oriented technology convergence models for the qualitative leap of the elderly care industry.

Keywords: Aged, Social Welfare, Case Management, Professionalism, Social Workers, Scoping Review

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

South Korea is approaching a super-aged society at an unprecedented speed, leading to an explosive increase in the social demand for elderly care. In response, the government has expanded public care systems, such as the Long-Term Care Insurance for the Aged (2008) and Community Care. However, despite the quantitative expansion, structural limitations such as fragmentation of service delivery, the small scale of providers, and the degradation of professionalism among care workers have emerged. In particular, social workers in the field are experiencing severe identity confusion. Theoretically, they are assigned the role of 'Case Managers' who assess the complex needs of the elderly and link resources. However, in reality, they are often perceived as 'administrators' performing administrative procedures rather than experts, due to excessive paperwork and performance pressure. Furthermore, role ambiguity and lack of information sharing with healthcare professionals (e.g.,

nurses) hinder integrated case management.

1.2 Objectives

This scoping review aims to systematically review domestic and international literature to identify realistic barriers hindering case management in the elderly care field and to analyze the gap between the ideal and reality of social workers' professional roles. The specific research questions are as follows:

1. What are the realistic barriers hindering case management practice in the elderly welfare field?
2. How does the gap between the ideal and reality of the social worker's professional role manifest?
3. What are the practical and policy alternatives to overcome the identified barriers and gaps?

2. Methods

2.1 Study Design

This study applies the scoping review methodology to identify research trends and map the scope of knowledge regarding case management professionalism in elderly welfare practice. The review follows the 5-stage framework proposed by Arksey and O'Malley (2005). This protocol is conducted in accordance with the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) checklist.

2.2 Search Strategy

The literature search was conducted as of November 2025 using major domestic and international academic databases.

1. Domestic Databases: RISS, DBpia, KISS.
2. International Databases: PubMed, Google Scholar, JAMA Network.
3. Search Terms (Keywords): Keywords were constructed based on the PCC (Population, Concept, Context) framework.
Population: Elderly/Older Adults, Social Worker.
Concept: Case Management, Professionalism, Role.
Context: Long-term Care, Elderly Welfare Practice.

2.3 Study Selection Inclusion Criteria:

1. Literature directly related to elderly care services.
2. Literature discussing the role, experience, and professionalism of case management personnel (social workers, nurses, care workers, etc.).
3. Literature including qualitative research, quantitative research, policy analysis, and literature reviews.

Study Selection Exclusion Criteria:

1. Non-academic materials such as simple business guides or columns.
2. Studies with low relevance to the topic (e.g., simple clinical treatment effects, architectural space analysis).

2.4 Data Charting and Analysis Data extraction will include key study characteristics such as: authors, year, study design, participants, concepts, and major findings. Data analysis employs a dual strategy:

1. Descriptive Statistics: Analyze macroscopic research trends such as publication trends by year, research subjects, and major keywords for the selected studies.
2. Thematic Analysis: Extract data on 'Ideal roles', 'Realistic barriers', and 'Key implications' from the final selected studies, and inductively categorize them to derive major discourse flows and issues.

2.5 Limitations This review will not conduct a formal quality appraisal of the included studies, as the purpose of a scoping review is to map the existing literature rather than to assess the quality of evidence. Grey literature may be partially excluded, which may limit comprehensiveness.

3. Implications

This review is expected to diagnose the qualitative crisis of case management practice in the quantitative expansion of Korean elderly care services. By identifying structural contradictions where social workers fall from 'psychosocial counselors' to 'administrative managers', and analyzing conflicts between professionals, this study will suggest legal grounds for care management and future-oriented technology convergence models (e.g., AI/ICT).

4. Dissemination Plan The findings will be disseminated through publication in a peer-reviewed journal and open-access repositories such as Zenodo.

5. Conflicts of Interest & Funding

The author declares no conflicts of interest relevant to this study. This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

References

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